

IMPORTANT ASPECTS OF CHILDREN'S EDUCATION**Adilbayeva Gulsaya Yerkin kizi****2nd year student of Chirchik State Pedagogical University,****Faculty of Preschool Education**

Abstract: The article provides an understanding of various information on child education, the development of children's personality, the creation of their educational foundations in a strong form, the methods of child education and the classification of their education methods.

Key words: Children, education, method, method, parental unity, sense, psyche, development, authoritarian, permission, given, competent, hereditary, environment, perception, understandable.

INTRODUCTION

Our ancestors paid special attention to the perfection of child education. They emphasized that the spiritual perfection of the human personality can be realized only on the basis of high manners and acquisition of science. For this, they say that it is necessary to pay serious attention to the education and development of the individual. A person is considered as the main subject and object of the educational system, as a consumer of educational services and as a provider of them. A person is a member of a certain society. The influence of social and biological factors on the comprehensive development of a person and his behavior is not always the same. Situations, tools, and social agents also affect his behavior and relations. Heredity, social environment, and education are of course important in the maturation of a person and his place in society. In whatever society a person lives, he matures based on the rules and regulations of the life of that society, the social climate of that society. And in turn, each person manifests himself differently. It differs by one's ability, one's place, character,

interest, level of mental development, need and attitude to work, attitude to the environment, ego. Education is pedagogy, that is, the science of child education. Education is a path, a path leading to goodness. If a person wants to mature, he must go through the education stage. Education is what makes a person human. It is no exaggeration to say that education is actually a system of heredity that is passed down from generation to generation. Because every person is the creator of the environment in which he developed.

Here's why every mental health problem is genetic. I must not forget one thing, the past will never be left behind, the childhood you lived will always remain inside you. You will be the educator as you were brought up. It is not for nothing that one of the famous representatives of Uzbek national culture, the enlightened poet, playwright, journalist, scientist Abdulla Avloni, said that "Education is for us: either life or death, or salvation or destruction, or happiness or disaster." A person does not become a child when he is born, unless he is educated before he is born. Educating a person to be perfect in all aspects is considered as the most urgent issue before the society, it is the eternal dream of our people, how our ancestors taught enlightenment, spirituality and culture to the young generation, the ways to lead them to perfection, the laws and regulations those who seek

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Nowadays, taking a comprehensive look at the issue of education has become an urgent issue. In fact, education is a very diverse concept. Everyone learns and educates differently. take a look around you, the person you are looking at today seems to be the same color. Each person has the color of his upbringing. You can only see these colors when you look deeper into it.

So what do you think, what kind of person are you and what kind of person are you raising? It is not an exaggeration that when you look at children, you will be delighted by their sincerity. But nowadays it seems that this sincerity is also

being hidden. It seems that the serious approach to children's education has disappeared. Parents were busy with work and worries and did not pay attention to their children's mental health. Of course, we cannot all say in this regard, however, such cases are clearly visible in our society. Child education is a very complicated matter. There are eight different stages of child care and upbringing, and when a child is born, five of these stages have passed. Umar Faruq Saido al-Jazari, one of the teachers of the Naqishbandi sect, says: "A child is a test at the same time. Did you educate him well, as in the pamphlet, did you teach him good and bad, did you teach him knowledge? If you don't do these things, you too will be considered a sinner." Basically, parents influence the child with their actions. Yes, we influence our children more with our actions than with advice. We should inculcate feelings of conscience, compassion, and kindness in our sons and daughters from childhood. If not, then it will be too late. Aren't these feelings the basis of humanity? Today, many people around us are raising children according to their own views. Let's take a look at the types of education and come to a conclusion about how right or wrong these views are. There are three types of education. These are: authoritarian, permissive and authoritative parenting. To give more information about these:

Authoritarian education: Parents play the main role in this type of education. Because parents have a strong influence on the child and make all the decisions for the child themselves. Authoritarian parents see children as inherently ignorant and incapable of rational thought. They expect children to follow without question. Authoritarian parents feel a great responsibility. When the children question their parents' behavior, the parents get angry and say, "How dare you disobey me?" I have done so much for you!" they scold. They do not consider themselves responsible for nurturing the child's emotional well-being, on the contrary, they believe that the child should blindly obey them. Such parents mainly raise children who are submissive, have no self-respect, cannot come to a

decision on their own, have no personal opinion and freedom. This way of theirs may be partially correct, but it would be better if they don't forget that the child is also a person who should have his freedoms and should be respected.

Permissive parenting: In this parenting method, parents follow a non-traditional parenting style. They have a soft and free spirit. Permissive parents do not want to impose rules on their children, and they go to great lengths to avoid confrontation with their children. These parents find it difficult to set boundaries with their children. Children's happiness is a key decision in the parenting process as they strive to meet the child's needs.

Permissive parents don't want to be the "bad person" or feel that their children hate them, so these parents prefer that the children make all the decisions and set their own rules. Permissive parents love their children and expect to be loved by their children because they treat them well. Only in some cases, such parents may produce an incompetent child, but this represents the least part of the statistics. Because this type of parents mainly raise capable, soft-spoken, sweet-spoken and kind children.

Authoritative discipline: This is a positive discipline style. This style of parenting is democratic, and both parents and children have a voice. Respectful parents seek to hear their children's opinions and opinions when solving problems and making big decisions, while maintaining parental authority. If the child does not meet the expectations of the parents, the parents have a nurturing attitude and try to solve the problem together with the child. Authoritative parents believe that mistakes are a great opportunity to learn. They help their children develop self-discipline and personal responsibility for their behavior. They believe that the respect between parent and child is mutual and that parents are positive role models for children. Children see themselves as belonging to a 'team' and strive to cooperate and contribute.

CONCLUSION

The authoritative style of parenting requires more work from parents than other styles. It's an intentional approach to parenting with long-term goals in mind. This type of parents raise children who are cooperative, leaders, leaders, who respect themselves and others, and who have a high moral level and culture.

So which of these do you think is correct? I hope you can come to the right conclusion for yourself. Now let's talk about the causes of bad situations in children's education:

1. The main reason for the emergence of qualities such as shyness in children is that they are not embraced by their parents. This seems like a normal situation, but it is like a failure in the stage of development of a child.

2. The lack of self-confidence in children is mainly due to the fact that the child was given enthusiasm by the parents or because the parents did not encourage him.

3. The reason for such a situation as aggression or quick outbursts of anger observed in children is the stubbornness of the parents to the child. For example, when a child demands something for himself, it is the unreasonable opposition of the parents.

4. Another bad feeling observed in children is their lack of respect for others. This is the loud appeal and shouting of the parents to the children.

5. It can be said that the lack of love given to the child by the parents is the reason for the children's aloofness, that is, they avoid others. Children will need more pampering.

6. One of the negative situations observed in most children is stinginess. The main reason for the appearance of this quality is when parents neglect the work of partnership with the child.

It is necessary to put an end to the development of such diseases in children. Their pure and innocent childhood should not be hindered. Today, most of the people around are people who have remained in their childhood. Pay more

attention to your children.

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